

BARGAINING THROUGH COMPETITION LAW?

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WITH CMA CONDUCT
REQUIREMENTS
IMPOSED ON GOOGLE

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Abstract

On 3 June 2026 the CMA imposed on Google its eagerly anticipated 'Publisher Conduct Requirement', under its powers in the Digital Markets, Competition and Consumers Act. The Publisher Conduct Requirement intends to address publishers' dissatisfaction with the use of their Search content in Google's AI services, by giving them the choice to withhold search content from generative AI use, and providing them with transparency and attribution. The CMA's conduct requirements are part of a wider trend in which competition authorities attempt to tackle the use of content in Search and AI training, fine-tuning and grounding. Competition authorities have joined the fray of the publishers' battle both for control over and remuneration for the use of their content by technology firms, be they digital (search or social) platforms or providers of integrated or standalone Generative AI services. This paper reflects on the Publisher Conduct Requirement within the wider context of both the general turn to competition authorities in the battle between publishers and AI (and search) for control over and remuneration for content, but also against the expectations on the CMA itself. It further reflects on whether competition authorities operate in the shadow of copyright, trying to reshape the bargaining process while not entirely accounting for the final shape of the underlying entitlements. The paper also queries the ability of competition law, even in its more flexible regulatory form, to solve what is fundamentally a structural sustainability problem for online content, news media, and cultural production in the age of AI. The paper signals a starting point for a further strand of research within CREATE on AI licensing and competition law.

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On 3 June 2026 the CMA imposed on Google its eagerly anticipated 'Publisher² Conduct Requirement'.³ This followed Google's designation as a firm with *Strategic Market Status* over search (and search advertising) under the Digital Markets, Competition and Consumers Act⁴ (DMCC Act) back in October 2025.⁵ The Publisher Conduct Requirement in essence directs Google to address publishers' dissatisfaction with the use of their content in its AI services, by:

- giving publishers control over whether their content that is used in Search can also be used by Google to train, fine-tune, or ground its generative AI services and features, including making sure they can choose to withhold their search content from Generative AI use (**choice**);
- giving publishers clear, comprehensible and user-friendly information on how Google uses their search content in its Generative AI services as well as on how users engage with that content (**transparency**);
- ensure that the content which is used in Generative AI features within Search is accurately and sufficiently attributed to publishers, so they can sustain their brand value and so that users can access the content and test its veracity (**attribution**).

The CMA's conduct requirements are part of a wider trend in which competition authorities attempt to tackle the use of content in Search and AI training, fine-tuning and grounding. Competition authorities have joined the fray of the publishers' battle both for control over and remuneration for the use of their content by technology firms, be they digital (search or social) platforms or providers of integrated or standalone Generative AI services.

The CMA's intervention this month is heavily focused on tackling the more traditional competition law aspects of this use of content: the leveraging of data advantages from Search into AI, and the barriers to entry such leveraging may create for the development of AI services by other firms than Google. Yet, the battle which is the background for this intervention more

² The term 'publisher' is understood widely in this context, as any party that makes content available on the web to persons using Google's general search services.

³ Competition and Markets Authority. 'CMA secures fairer deal for publishers and improves Google search services in UK' (3 June 2026), available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/news/cma-secures-fairer-deal-for-publishers-and-improves-google-search-services-in-uk> accessed on 10 June 2026.

⁴ Digital Markets, Competition and Consumers Act 2024 ('DMCC Act'), <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2024/13/contents>.

⁵ Competition and Markets Authority. 'CMA confirms Google has strategic market status in search services' (10 October 2025), available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/news/cma-confirms-google-has-strategic-market-status-in-search-services> accessed on 10 June 2026.

broadly concerns the bargaining power of publishers and their⁶ demands to be compensated for the use of content they have created.

Publishers – not only press ‘publishers’ in the narrow sense but any content creators offering their content on the web – are at the centre of several distinct legal, regulatory and policy battles. These battles illustrate the challenges which arise when a new technology creates a problem that falls, simultaneously, into the remits of several areas of law and policy, each of which may have different conceptual starting points and analytical approaches, and come with distinct enforcement powers.

Different interest groups and policy makers are looking at the same underlying phenomenon – that AI systems are trained on creative content, but are displacing the revenue of those who created that content – but through very different lenses. Let us take stock of the call upon competition law in this context, and the likely relationships with copyright questions.

From copyright to competition: publishers searching for leverage

Press publishers in particular came to competition law with a specific hope: that the competition authorities might force the question of fair terms onto the table. Initially, they hoped that competition authorities could respond to a near-existential impasse in their relationship with Search: search engines (and social media) use content without paying publishers for it – or at least not a level of remuneration which is sufficient to offset the losses in advertising revenue which have followed the digital revolution; at the same time, publishers were dependent on these search (and social) platforms to reach the customers they had left. Eventually, what started as a search problem became even more acute as AI emerged: AI systems do not just index content, they answer queries directly. This makes them more of a threat to existing business models than search, because AI may displace content providers entirely rather than simply diverting revenue from traffic.

Originally, the attempt to solve the question of remuneration – at EU level – took the form of an introduction of new legal rights, at least for news media. Article 15 of the CDSM Directive⁷ introduced a neighbouring right for press publishers, offering publishers of press publications exclusive rights to authorise the online use of their press publications by information society

⁶ Or at least of vocal groups of publishers, particularly in news media.

⁷ EU Directive on Copyright in the Digital Single Market: Directive 2019/790 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on copyright and related rights in the Digital Single Market and amending Directives 96/9/EC and 2001/29/EC, OJ L 130/92, <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2019/790/oj>.

providers. They would have the exclusive rights to authorise or prohibit the reproduction and making available to the public of their publications.

The CDSM Directive seemed to fall short, however. In 2019, Google announced in France (the first Member State to implement the CDSM Directive into national law⁸) that it would no longer display previews of European press publishers' content in search results, unless a publisher opted into such display, with no remuneration for the use of such content. French publishers turned to the French competition authority for help, pleading that the imbalance in power between them and Google made this a matter for competition law. They argued that Google's market power enabled it to refuse to pay them for their content 'in circumvention of the *spirit* (if not the letter) of copyright law. The Authority agreed: it saw the potential for an abuse of dominance because, by not negotiating payment for the use of content, in its view Google's actions did not align with what the Authority perceived as the goal of the law, namely to redefine the sharing of value in favour of press publishers, within a negotiated framework.⁹ The Authority was concerned that Google had in fact arrived at an even better commercial and competitive position than it was in before the law was adopted. This concern was further exacerbated when, after years of back-and-forth, Google started using publishers' content in AI without offering a meaningful opt-out to publishers, prompting the Authority to impose further sanctions on the company.¹⁰

The French intervention was heralded as brave by commentators within the news industry, with some hoping that other competition authorities might follow suit.¹¹ In the UK, the hope in press

⁸ Ula Furgał, 'The implementation of the press publishers' right in the CDSM Directive: lessons from France', CREATE blog (31 March 2020), <https://www.create.ac.uk/blog/2020/03/31/the-implementation-of-the-press-publishers-right-in-the-cdsm-directive-lesson-from-france/>. It is also noteworthy that, at the time of writing, a revision of the national law is under consideration to further strengthen the neighbouring rights provisions, apparently following the imbalances which are discussed in the following paragraphs of this piece. See: Proposition de loi, T.A. n 250, https://www.assemblee-nationale.fr/dyn/17/textes/l17t0250_texte-adopte-seance accessed 10 June 2026.

⁹ Autorité de la Concurrence, Décision 20-MC-01 du 09 avril 2020, relative à des demandes de mesures conservatoires présentées par le Syndicat des éditeurs de la presse magazine, l'Alliance de la presse d'information générale e.a. et l'Agence France-Presse, <https://www.autoritedelaconcurrence.fr/fr/decision/relative-des-demandes-de-mesures-conservatoires-presentees-par-le-syndicat-des-editeurs-de>, accessed 10 June 2026.

¹⁰ Autorité de la Concurrence, Décision 24-D-03 du 15 mars 2024 relative au respect des engagements figurant dans la décision de l'Autorité de la concurrence n° 22-D-13 du 21 juin 2022 relative à des pratiques mises en œuvre par Google dans le secteur de la presse, <https://www.autoritedelaconcurrence.fr/fr/decision/relative-au-respect-des-engagements-figurant-dans-la-decision-de-lautorite-de-la-0>, accessed 10 June 2026.

¹¹ News Media Association, 'NMA Welcomes Decision To Sanction Google For Failure To Pay For Content' (NMA, 15 July 2021), <https://newsmediauk.org/blog/2021/07/15/nma-welcomes-decision-to-sanction-google-for-failure-to-pay-for-content/> accessed 10 June 2026; European Publishers Council, 'EPC Welcomes the French Competition Authority's decision: Google to pay the French Press Publishes' (10 April 2020) <https://www.epceurope.eu/post/epc-welcomes-the-french-competition-authority-s-decision-google-to-pay-the-french-press-publishes>, accessed 10 June 2026; Alliance Presse, 'Autorité de la concurrence: Google doit négocier avec les éditeurs de presse pour la rémunération de leurs contenus'

publisher quarters appeared to be that the CMA may follow the lead of its French counterpart, not under traditional competition law but within the more flexible framework the DMCCA created for it.¹²

However, so far, the CMA has appeared to act more cautiously, focusing its attention on issues which fall the most neatly in a competition law scope: that where a single firm transfers power from one market to another. Despite initial indications that the CMA may be willing to more directly intervene in the bargaining of terms between publishers and Google (for Search and AI), it has held off (for now) from directly forcing Google to negotiate fair terms with publishers. What is more, the CMA has not established any general industry-wide principles for bargaining on content for AI training, fine-tuning, or grounding, but focused its efforts on a single firm.

The reach of the CMA's Publisher Conduct Requirements

In one way, the CMA did pick up where the French authority left off: Google's use of search content in Generative AI. Its focus from the outset has been on giving all (not just press) publishers controls that enable them to withhold the use of their content from Google's generative AI services without affecting their position in Google's general search (which could otherwise reduce their search traffic). In addition, it aims to enable publishers to obtain the information needed to make an informed choice, and to trust that Google will attribute their content when it is used.¹³

The CMA relied on its powers under the DMCC Act, rather than competition law in a strict sense, to do so. It can be queried whether the CMA needed the DMCC Act to achieve these obligations *in substance*. The choice, transparency, and attribution conduct requirements do not deviate much from the principles under competition law, and perhaps similar obligations could be imposed under competition law itself. (A similar concern seems to also have spurred an

(AP, 9 April 2020) <https://www.alliancepresse.fr/actualite/autorite-de-la-concurrence-google-doit-negocier-avec-les-editeurs-de-presse-pour-la-remuneration-de-leurs-contenus/> accessed 10 June 2026; Alexandre Piquard, 'Droit d'auteur : Google sommé de négocier avec les médias pour rémunérer la reprise d'extraits de contenus', *Le Monde* (9 April 2020) https://www.lemonde.fr/economie/article/2020/04/09/droit-d-auteur-l-autorite-de-la-concurrence-donne-raison-aux-medias-contre-google_6036097_3234.html accessed 10 June 2026.

¹² News Media Association, 'NMA Responds To CMA Designation Of Google Search' (NMA, 10 October 2025), <https://newsmediauk.org/blog/2025/10/10/nma-responds-to-cma-designation-of-google-search/> accessed 10 June 2026.

¹³ See its January consultation: Competition and Markets Authority, Consultation: Publisher Conduct Requirement, Google's general search services (28 January 2026) https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/6979d0bf75d44370965520a0/Publisher_conduct_requirement.pdf accessed 10 June 2026; as well as its final Publisher Conduct Requirement decision in June: Competition and Markets Authority, Publisher Conduct Requirement, Google's general search services (3 June 2026) https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/6a1f0098b95db968c8f3bdb9/Publisher_CR_final_decision.pdf accessed 10 June 2026 ('Final Publisher CR decision').

investigation by the European Commission under traditional competition law rules.¹⁴) Yet, it is the *enforcement* flexibility under the DMCC Act that gave the CMA more leeway to act, as it provides the CMA with a more flexible and dialogue-based approach to enforcement than competition law.

Under the DMCC Act, firms can be designated as having Strategic Market Status (SMS) over a specific digital activity if they have substantial and entrenched market power and a position of strategic significance in respect of that digital activity.¹⁵ Once a firm has been designated as having SMS, the CMA can impose conduct requirements without having to prove harm in the same way as in a finding of a violation of competition law. Conduct requirements can include obligations or prohibitions to achieve one or more of the three objectives set out in the DMCC Act: “fair dealing,” “open choices,” or “trust and transparency.”¹⁶

These conduct requirements can be closely related to ‘traditional’ competition law cases, for example prohibiting the SMS firm from using the power it has over one digital activity to treat its other (digital) products more favourably, or prohibiting an SMS firm from restricting interoperability between its services and that of other companies. The conduct requirements could also go further, taking a broader interpretation of such obligations as those to ‘trade on fair and reasonable terms’ or prohibitions not to apply ‘discriminatory terms, conditions or policies to certain users’ beyond those which directly undermine competition.¹⁷

This breadth of possible conduct requirements gave the CMA the ability both to reproduce competition law-style remedies in a more flexible manner, and to push further through the regulatory vocabulary of fairness and bargaining. This is why some disappointment can now be heard in publisher circles, as some believed that the CMA would take more interventionist steps to substantively address publisher concerns around remuneration than the ones we have seen so far.

As Ula Furgał and I explained on a ProMarket blog last year,¹⁸ the DMCC Act actually gives the CMA the power to force an SMS firm to adopt fair and reasonable payment terms towards specific

¹⁴ European Commission. ‘Commission opens investigation into possible anticompetitive conduct by Google in the use of online content for AI purposes’ (9 December 2025) https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/da/ip_25_2964 accessed 10 June 2026.

¹⁵ DMCC Act, n 4, section 2.

¹⁶ DMCC Act, n 4, section 19.

¹⁷ DMCC Act, n 4, section 20.

¹⁸ Ula Furgał and Magali Eben, ‘The UK’s Path to Sustainable Journalism in the Marketplace of Ideas’, ProMarket blog (26 February 2025) <https://www.promarket.org/2025/02/26/the-uks-path-to-sustainable-journalism-in-the-marketplace-of-ideas/> accessed 10 June 2026.

third parties.¹⁹ Some commentators believed that the CMA could oblige Google or Facebook (or any other significant gateway to news and advertising) to provide reasonable and fair payment terms to those news publishers whose content they host.

In 2025 the CMA indeed hinted at an intention to use its powers to address the imbalance in bargaining power between Google and publishers. In June last year, the CMA published a 'Roadmap' of possible conduct requirements.²⁰ The roadmap identified three categories of conduct requirements it could impose, which decreasing degrees of priority or immediacy. Publisher concerns popped up both in category 1 and category 2.

Category 1 were the concerns and interventions of highest priority on which the CMA would 'consult shortly after' the designation decision. In these, the CMA indicated it would act to ensure publishers have 'effective transparency, attribution and choice in how their content collected by Google for Search is used in AI-generated responses, including AI Overviews and Gemini AI Assistant, without affecting if and how they appear in Google Search'.²¹ These became the Publisher Conduct Requirement.

Meanwhile, category 2 concerns were 'subject to further analysis', and the CMA intended to consult on or launch investigations for in the first half of 2026. There, the CMA considered a more direct intervention in the terms for the use of content. These would respond to 'publisher concerns about the impact of Google's bargaining position, and whether they are receiving fair and reasonable terms (including payment terms)'.²² By articulating them as category 2 concerns, the CMA indicated it could potentially use its powers to directly address the question of actual remuneration for the use of publishers' content, but postponed this question of remuneration to a later date. One which has yet to come.

The question of fair terms deferred

Now it is clear that the question of fair terms is not immediately on the table. The category 2 concerns have not been turned into actual conduct requirements. Recently, in June 2026, the CMA proceeded to imposing the category 1 conduct requirements articulated above (choice, transparency, attribution), while expressly leaving category 2 concerns to the side. It did not rule out having to 'bring forward work on further measures to ensure a fair exchange between Google

¹⁹ DMCC Act, n 4, section 20 and section 38.

²⁰ Competition and Markets Authority, 'Strategic market status investigation into Google's general search services. Roadmap of possible measures to improve competition in search' (24 June 2025) https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/6859810e00006f6419fade671/Roadmap_.pdf accessed 10 June 2026.

²¹ Roadmap, n 20, para 1.5.

²² Roadmap, n 20, para 1.6.

and publishers',²³ but clearly hopes the category 1 Publisher Conduct Requirement will sufficiently redress the imbalance so that it does not have to. It promised to 'closely monitor the impacts' the conduct requirement has on 'the ability of publishers to secure fair remuneration for their content'.

The concern that seems to underpin the (Category 1) conduct requirements imposed in June 2026 is essentially a leveraging risk: a fear that control of content in search can be leveraged into power in AI. It still refers to the broader concerns that publishers have over their own future by articulating that expected benefits would include 'supporting the viability of web publishers' business models, including by improving the bargaining position of the publishers to negotiate deals with Google, and allowing publishers to maintain the web traffic needed to monetise content'.²⁴ At the same time, the conduct that is being addressed is more narrowly the extension of power from one activity to the other through the use of data in one service that was initially collected for another service.

This is not surprising, given that the previous work the CMA has done on AI Foundation Models²⁵ put significant emphasis on the way the need to obtain large datasets may constitute barriers to entry into AI markets and the fact that companies with previous datasets – from search engines or media platforms – may have a competitive advantage in generative AI.

To the CMA's credit, it meaningfully adjusted its conduct requirements to address valid input arising out of the public consultations. The CMA has undertaken a very diligent and evidence-based approach in adopting these conduct requirements. In many ways, its intervention is brave and robust, at a time when its activities are under intense political and public scrutiny for their impact on growth, investment, and productivity in the UK.

Bargaining in the shadow of copyright

The actions of the CMA and other competition authorities raise questions for copyright policy. Competition authorities are not in substance enforcing copyright law, but what they do has implications for a potential reform of copyright law and for how bargaining happens in copyright-mediated markets.

²³ Final Publisher CR decision, n 13, para 3.22.

²⁴ Final Publisher CR decision, n 13, para 1.10.

²⁵ The CMA's AI Foundation Models initial review (2023) and update paper and technical update report (2024) are available on the CMA's website: <https://www.gov.uk/cma-cases/ai-foundation-models-initial-review>.

First, because there has been an attempt to prompt competition authorities to use their powers where copyright is perceived as falling short, *not in the law in its substance, but in the bargaining framework surrounding copyright law*.

This can be seen quite vividly in the French intervention, where the French authority stepped in to fix an apparent gap in the actual achievements of the CDSM Directive's neighbouring rights for publishers – a gap which stemmed from the imbalance of power between search providers (and AI) and publishers.

Second, because the battle about copyright entitlements online and the sense and nonsense of opt-in, opt-out and licenses provides the legal context in which the terms for Search and AI use of publisher content are set.

The French authority grounded its analysis on copyright law (or at least, neighbouring rights pursuant to the CDSM Directive) more clearly than other authorities, and certainly more explicitly than the CMA. But the spectre of copyright policy also haunts the interventions in the UK, even if the CMA does not ground its decisions in copyright *law*.

Stakeholders responded to CMA's intended conduct requirements by raising their relationship (and potential contradictions) with the EU CDSM Directive and with UK Government's policy work on AI and copyright. The CMA responded that the UK government's policy work is separate and ongoing,²⁶ while the Publisher Conduct Requirement is a standalone requirement independent of policy on copyright.²⁷ Yet the CMA's position is not as categorical as it may seem. Its decision explicitly aims to address the risks that Google may use open-source datasets to acquire publisher content despite their opt-outs. Here, the CMA acknowledges stakeholders' concerns that Google may use datasets in a context where legality is contested or subject to lower levels of legal protection.²⁸ While the CMA does not address these concerns when in the conduct requirements decision, it is useful to read this decision in combination with its Foundation Models Reviews.

The CMA 2023 report noted the increasing importance of propriety data for a variety of reasons and the increases in partnerships involving data or agreements to licence data. It noted its concerns that large technology firms may use their existing strong positions to secure such

²⁶ Stakeholders also referred to the EU's CDSM Directive, as noted by the CMA.

²⁷ Final Publisher CR decision, n 13, para 3.17.

²⁸ Final Publisher CR decision, n 13, para 3.19.

agreements.²⁹ While its 2023 report noted that crowd-sourced data is perceived by some stakeholders as presenting advantages because there are ‘fewer issues relating to copyright and privacy’,³⁰ the CMA’s reports seem to recognise that this depends significantly on the entitlements copyright law or regulation endows publishers with, particularly if scraping requires their opt-in. Its 2024 report specifically refers to the uncertainty of the potential enforcement of copyright law relating to the use of web crawled training data and ongoing litigation.³¹ The CMA recognises that ‘as more clarity emerges on the various legal debates’,... ‘imbalances may emerge between early movers and later entrants in terms of the ability to have trained models on web-scraped data’.³²

As my colleagues Ula Furgał and Martin Kretschmer noted, private bargaining ‘takes place “in the shadow of the law”’. It is the preferences, expectations and uncertainties that (rational) parties bring to negotiations that result in different outcomes. The law intervenes in multiple ways. It may grant endowments, such as rights, that may function as bargaining chips. It may regulate enforcement which enables parties to bind each other. It may condition process and who sits around the table.’³³

When it comes to the use of content in Search and AI, the CMA’s intervention is best understood as one which conditions the process and who sits around the table.

When it comes to the publishers’ battle over the use of their content, competition law (and regulation) appears to intervene primarily on the process, giving one group the levers to negotiate from a (potentially) stronger position and forcing one firm to engage with this group. Competition law cannot, in theory, grant endowments which fall within the prerogative of another legislator or enforcer, which has not yet acted to grant or strengthen them (such as copyright law). In France, however, this did not stop the French authority from trying to fill out endowments where the letter of copyright law fell short. In the UK, the CMA has held back from doing that, focusing instead on trying to set the conditions in which negotiation may happen.

²⁹ Competition and Markets Authority, *AI Foundation Models: Initial Report* (18 September 2023) para 3.7. https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/650449e86771b90014fdab4c/Full_Non-Confidential_Report_PDFA.pdf accessed 10 June 2026.

³⁰ CMA *AI Foundational Models 2023*, n 29, para 3.13.

³¹ Competition and Markets Authority, *AI Foundation Models: Technical update report* (16 April 2024) https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/661e5a4c7469198185bd3d62/AI_Foundation_Models_technical_update_report.pdf accessed 10 June 2026.

³² CMA *AI Foundation Models Technical Update Report 2024*, 31, para 3.8.

³³ Ula Furgał and Martin Kretschmer, *Bargaining in the Shadow of the Press Publishers’ Right*, CREATE Working Paper 2024/4, p.4, available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10948500>; now published as Ula Furgał and Martin Kretschmer, ‘Bargaining in the shadow of the press publishers’ right’. In: Senftleben, Martin, Irion, Kristina, McGonagle, Tarlach and Poort, Joost (eds.) *Cambridge Handbook on Media Law and Policy in Europe* (2026 Cambridge University Press).

It may be too early to tell how effective the CMA's strategy here is. The CMA itself notes that some deals between Google and publishers are already being struck. Which raises the question: is the CMA's action adding to negotiating position that already exists in the shadow of copyright? Or is it substituting for it? And if publishers' withholding of consent for use of their content already gives them some leverage in negotiations, what is the marginal effect of a competition intervention that is limited to one dominant player?

That last point is crucial: what the CMA has done here is set conditions of conduct for *one* firm, not set an industry-wide standard for negotiations. Although the CMA articulates its desire to put publishers in a better position to negotiate fair terms, this is at most the case for terms set between publisher and Google, not publishers and other AI developers.

What is more, its focus has been limited to the kind of conduct that might enable Google to transfer its advantages in activity (search) to another (AI). It is not a wholesale consideration of the way content is obtained and used in AI in general, and does not address remaining imbalances in power in the obtention of data directly for AI training, fine-tuning and grounding without Search as an intermediary.

One way to put this into perspective is to ask about the CMA's focus in a hypothetical scenario: if publishers were in a position to get 'fair' terms so beneficial that they *en masse* agreed to allow Google access to all their content for AI training – perhaps because in this idealised scenario Google pays them enough to offset revenue decline from drop in traffic – would the CMA still be concerned? After all, then the issue of unfair terms would no longer be at play, but the leveraging of content to boost Google's position would be. As the CMA noted in its CMA foundation models review, it is worried about concentration of access to data in hands of a few – particularly the established big tech players.

The CMA's endeavour to shape the process cannot be wholly disconnected from the underlying endowments. In theory, the endowments are shaped by copyright policy (or other areas of policy, such as data protection, subsidies, etc), not competition law. Yet competition decisions are shaped by and influencing these endowments. The CMA's concern about open-source datasets and the contested legality, mentioned above, shows it is already brushing up against copyright and privacy questions. If copyright policy were to move – say to an opt-out regime or a research

exception³⁴ – this may reshape the bargaining chips in ways which the competition framework has not yet accounted for.

There are also more granular questions about how the conduct requirements interact with the assumptions in copyright policy. The definition of publishers does not engage with the (possible) distinction between rightsholders and authors. Instead, it is concerned with who makes content discoverable to Google’s crawler rather than with the strict copyright ownership over the content. It does not account for such copyright distinctions explicitly, even though who has the ability to actually negotiate remuneration may depend on the volume of content over which they have rights.

Whether the CMA, and competition authorities more generally, can meaningfully affect bargaining in the shadow of copyright remains to be seen. There is an important empirical question about the relationship between competition interventions and the licensing deals that are already being struck in the industry. CREATE research is building the evidence base, mapping the licensing agreements made public.³⁵ A tentative question is whether the industry has already shifted to certain practices and standards to acquire data, which may become difficult to shift through ad hoc interventions. An interesting observation based on the data gathered by Thomas and Kretschmer is that press publishers have made up a significant proportion of the licensing agreements, so that they perhaps need less help to organise themselves than more disparate content creators on the internet without large associations representing them.

It should be acknowledged that, although the CMA is doing impressive work here, the author of this paper remains sceptical that competition law (including the DMCC Act) can solve what is ultimately a sustainability problem: an existential issue about the viability of content businesses online that goes well beyond what any competition authority is equipped to fix.

The CMA puts numbers on the value its conduct requirements will bring to publishers. I am not persuaded that this addresses the structural question. Yet, how much of this value is a one-off? How much is sustained over time? And how much do publishers actually need to survive longer term – and to have sufficient breathing room to adapt their business models, or to develop the creative solutions to the threats to their survival that the current moment demands? For publishers of particular societal importance, the question of whether competition law can

³⁴ CREATE team, ‘Academic research and Government policy on AI and copyright’, CREATE blog (30 March 2026), <https://www.create.ac.uk/blog/2026/03/30/academic-research-and-government-policy-on-ai-and-copyright/> accessed 10 June 2026.

³⁵ Amy Thomas and Martin Kretschmer, ‘The AI licensing economy’, CREATE blog (24 February 2025), <https://www.create.ac.uk/blog/2025/02/24/the-ai-licensing-economy/> accessed 10 June 2026.

provide the support needed is one we should answer honestly. My view is that it cannot. Competition law can correct bargaining imbalances and redress the competitive advantages of single firms. It cannot substitute for a considered policy response to the structural economics of news markets and cultural heritage in the age of AI.

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